

Quantitative Analysis of Vegetation Indices as Discriminators Between Different Crop Categories

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Abstract

Monitoring vegetation health is crucial for assessing ecosystem stability amidst climate change and environmental degradation. Hyperspectral imaging provides detailed data that can be systematized using various vegetation indices. Vegetation indices represent expert-determined values with relevance in analyzing plant growth and vigor dynamics or in sensing plant water status, among others. Many practical applications are built upon analysis of vegetation indices values. In this paper we investigate their discriminative power as features of a classifier and what is their relative importance in this discrimination. The proposed method involves a random forest classifier and is evaluated in context of agriculture crop segmentation on UAV-HSI database. Results indicate medium-to-strong discriminative power and relatively comparable importance, with none of the indices being dominant.

Keywords— remote sensing, vegetation indices, random forest, ranking

1 Introduction

Perhaps¹ the most remarkable digital transformation we are witnessing today in the field of agriculture is the introduction of digitization and artificial intelligence as a low cost alternative to what used to be human taken decisions. Over the past few decades, a multitude of applications based on measurement data have revolutionized agriculture. Digital data from on-site, proximal, and satellite-level measurements provide valuable insights into the condition and health of agricultural crops. A powerful source of information is due to remote sensing, as it offer views of fields significantly larger than a human eye can. For agricultural crops, remote sensed information provides indication of growth, vigor, and their dynamics from terrestrial vegetation. This information provides an objective basis for the macro and micromanagement (depending on resolution) of agricultural production, but, also in many occasions, the necessary information for yield estimation of crops.

Often, the remote sensed data is in the form of multispectral or hyperspectral imaging which are means to a holistically investigate what is beyond the human perception. Two popular sources for such data are: satellite imaging and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) imaging.

¹Preprint. Authoritative version can be followed on IEEEExplore web-site.

Regarding platforms, satellite-based remote sensing offers increasing spatial, spectral and temporal resolution, enabling the extraction of long-term data series that are consistent, comparable, and cost-effective [1]. Moreover, some satellite platforms, like Sentinel 2, Landsat 7-8, provide free access to visible and multispectral data. Yet, satellite data yield two main challenges with respect to the precision agriculture: the per pixel resolution (10 *m* for Sentinel, 30 *m* per pixel for Landsat and 250 *m* for MODIS) and the orbit period (16 days for Landsat and 26 days for SPOT and 12 for Sentinel).

Complementary and alternatively, airborne and, more recently, UAV platforms can be utilized. However, the former can be cost-prohibitive due to the need for expensive aircraft and pilots. In contrast, UAV platforms have become nearly ubiquitous in the past years, offering affordable aircraft and camera payloads that range from visible to hyperspectral. This technology, known as Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS), includes mainly fixed-wing and multirotor options. Battery-powered multirotor UAS with high payload capacities have a limited flight time, currently around 15 to 25 minutes. Despite this, these UAS can achieve higher spatial and temporal data resolution, enabling precision agriculture applications with sub-meter per pixel resolution. This permits more thorough research and practical applications such as irrigation scheduling, and modeling evapotranspiration [1].

The capture of electromagnetic wave reflectance information from canopies, in remote sensing imaging, unveils additional information. The reflectance of light spectra from plants varies with plant type, water content within tissues, and other intrinsic factors [2]. The reflectance of vegetation in the electromagnetic spectrum (spectral reflectance or emission characteristics of vegetation) is determined by the chemical and morphological characteristics of the surfaces of organs or leaves [3]. The main applications for remote sensing of vegetation utilize the following light spectra [4]:

- the ultraviolet region (UV) from 10 to 380 nm;
- the visible (VIS) spectra, which include blue (450-495 nm), green (495-570 nm), and red (620-750 nm) wavelength regions, and
- the near and mid-infrared band (850-1700 nm) - NIR.

Vegetation indices derived from various ranges light spectra provide insights into various plant characteristics, beyond growth and vigor, such as water content, pigments, sugar and carbohydrate levels, protein content, and aromatic compounds [5]. Different applications rely on the reflectivity peaks or overtones of specific compounds within the visible and near/mid-infrared regions of the light spectra [1].

In prior art, a very wide set of vegetation indices have been proposed [6]. In this paper we assume a machine learning perspective, and, starting from the observation that vegetation indices, at their core, are expert derived features, we investigate automatically their discriminative power in a context of semantic segmentation. Given a collection of UAV hyperspectral images having mask annotation with crops, we use a random forest to: (i) establish the power of vegetation indices as discriminative features when compared to raw hyper-pixels and (ii) to rank the indices envisaged based on the importance in building the classification system.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 review previous works that analyze comparatively various vegetation indices, section 3 presents the database, the envisaged vegetation indices and the machine learning system. Section 4 presents results and comments. The paper ends with discussion and conclusions.

2 Prior work

Since multiple vegetation indices have been proposed, detailed definition would take exhaustive space and to make the presentation more efficient we will refer to them by

their acronym (as it is common in the field) and kindly refer the reader to work of Radovcaj et al. [6] for thorough taxonomy.

Comparative analysis of various vegetation indexes has been aimed before. Comparisons have been carried in general and emphasized quantitative and qualitative differences. For instance, Payero et al. [7] compared 11 indices in terms of correlation with respect to plant height for alfalfa and grass; they have found at least medium correlation for all and strong for variation of vegetation indices (VI): Band Ratio (RATIO), TVI, NDVI, and IPVI. In the same line, Cao et al. [8] used different satellites and the corresponding images of a mountain and investigated differences in gamut and accuracy; they have found that in those condition NDVI saturates earlier than SAVI and VIUPD.

A significant amount of work was put in establishing the capability of vegetation indices to predict the green leaf area, which may be seen a classification between green and bare soils patches. Vina et al. [9] looked into physical and chemical background of various indices to establish rank. Towers et al. [10] tasked themselves with establishing differences between the accuracy of leaf canopy between several indices for vineyards; for that specific scenario, which involved linear and logarithmic regression, NDVI was found as the most accurate and $SAVI_2$ as the best indicator of leaf area.

In terms of suitability for crop identification, Mroz et al. [11] compared several vegetation indices as basis to form time series and, from there, to infer the crop from a list that is common in a location (Poland) and includes winter wheat, spring wheat, sugar beet, winter and spring rapeseed, maize; they have found that all VI-s have similar significance and usefulness, when the measure was based on conditional linear regression. Similarly, but focusing on the contrast in imaging for different patches of crops, Yeom et al. [12] looked at indices calculable from UAV mounted multispectral camera; they have found that near-infrared (NIR) based indices offer the best contrast and there is little difference among them.

In summary, while comparative analysis have been carried, they had refer to specific aspects which did not include discriminative power as basis for semantic segmentation (which is inherently a supervised machine learning task) and have focused only on small samples.

3 Method and materials

In this work, for the analysis of the images, ten vegetation indices have been used and were computed with specific formulas. For example, NDVI, is a measurement of a green and healthy vegetation which, thanks to the combination of normalised difference formulation and use of the highest absorption and reflectance regions of chlorophyll, make it a reliable parameter over a wide range of conditions. The other indices that were used in this project are LAI, DVI, SAVI, VARI, GNDVI, ARVI, EVI, GEMI and GARI [6].

3.1 Dataset

The dataset used in this project, UAV-HSI [13], is publicly available² and it consists of two sub-regions, Makialou Village’s plots (MJK_N, MJK_S) and Xijingmeng Valliange’s plots (XJM). The hyperspectral data was obtained on September 18th, 2019 with an electric hexacopter. The UAV carried the sensor Pika L hyperspectral image made by Resonon company, which has a spectral range of 385nm to 1034nm with a total of 200 bands. The database is annotated, at pixels level with 30 classes with

²The database can be downloaded at: <https://www.scidb.cn/en/detail?dataSetId=6de15e4ec9b74dacab12e29cb557f041>

uneven distribution. Details about crop distribution acquisition equipment may be retrieve from the accompanying article [13].

3.2 Vegetation Indices

The main point of this paper is to analyze which one of the vegetation indices is able to have a more important role in training the model. In this evaluation 10 VIs have been considered. The calculation of the vegetation indices for each pixel in the hyperspectral images used the following formulas:

1. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}} \quad (1)$$

2. Leaf Area Index (LAI) using Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)

$$\text{EVI} = 2.5 \times \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + 6 \times \text{Red} - 7.5 \times \text{Blue} + 1}$$

$$\text{LAI} = 3.618 \times \text{EVI} - 0.118 \quad (2)$$

3. Difference Vegetation Index (DVI)

$$\text{DVI} = \text{NIR} - \text{Red} \quad (3)$$

4. Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)

$$\text{SAVI} = \frac{(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) \times (1 + L)}{(\text{NIR} + \text{Red} + L)} \quad (4)$$

where L is an adjustment factor. Usually $L = 0.5$.

5. Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI)

$$\text{VARI} = \frac{\text{Green} - \text{Red}}{\text{Green} + \text{Red} - \text{Blue}} \quad (5)$$

6. Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

$$\text{GNDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Green}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Green}} \quad (6)$$

7. Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index

$$\text{ARVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - (\text{Red} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))}{\text{NIR} + (\text{Red} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))} \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma = 1.7$.

8. Enhanced Vegetation Index

$$\text{EVI} = 2.5 \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + 6 \times \text{Red} - 7.5 \times \text{Blue} + 1} \quad (8)$$

9. Global Environmental Monitoring Index

$$\text{GEMI} = \eta(1 - 0.25 * \eta) - \frac{\text{Red} - 0.125}{1 - \text{Red}} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\eta = \frac{2(\text{NIR}^2 - \text{Red}^2) + 1.5 * \text{NIR} + 0.5 * \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red} + 0.5} \quad (10)$$

10. Green Atmospherically Resistant Index

$$\text{GARI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - (\text{Green} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))}{\text{NIR} + (\text{Green} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))} \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma = 1.7$.

Figure 1: Relative importance of the vegetation indices in the 30-class problem.

Table 1: Average accuracy on 30-class problem

Classifier	Feature	AvgAccuracy
SegNet [13]		43.61
UNet [13]		76.07
TransUNet [13]		78.64
HSI-TransUNet [13]		86.05
RF	Raw pixels	69.98
RF	Veg Indices	57.27

3.3 Classifier and feature importance

The segmentation problem is treated as a pixel-wise independent supervised classification. The classifier, a random forest with 40 trees, has the advantage of being able to offer feature importance too. While deep learning semantic segmentation has been attempted on the problem with accurate results [13], deep learning models are developing features themselves in the training process, and, thus, are improper to feed them with expert derived features, such as vegetation indices.

The importance (i.e. ranking) of features is determined as the mean and standard deviation of accumulation of the impurity (i.e Gini Index) decrease when that feature is used in a node [14].

4 Implementation and results

4.1 Implementation

Following the introductory paper [13], the data is pre-structured into training and testing subsets. Each image consists of 96×96 pixels with 200 spectral bands. The labels are associated to categories, ranging from 1 to 30 representing different vegetation classes. The significance of the spectral bands is described in the introductory paper and in camera manual; the latter also presents formulas for vegetation indices. The solution has been implemented in Python.

4.2 Performance Evaluation

The performance is evaluated, following [13], with the average accuracy, which is the average of the accuracies of the 30 classes.

Two kinds of experiments have considered: multi-class and one-vs-all.

Table 2: Average accuracy on for chosen crops when on-vs-all scenario was envisaged

Crop	Bare soil weed	Chinese cabbage	Corn	Millet	Beans
AvgAcc.	87.65	87.40	89.30	90.74	92.40

Figure 2: Examples of hyperspectral images, rendered as RGB color components, followed by $\gamma = 1.5$ contrast adjustment, with the five crops selected for one-vs-all scenario

Multi-class. In this case, the database is used as provided, with labels containing 30 classes. Here, the baseline performance can be established in two forms: the classifier is random forest but input data are the, raw, 200-dimensional hyperpixels and, respectively, the semantic segmentation algorithm with visual transformer models as used in [13]. The results may be seen in Table 1.

Two observations are at hand: (i) The vegetation indices have less discriminatory power than using all spectra, but taking into account than most are computed in several (more precisely, just 4) bands, the reduction is less dramatic. (ii) Pixel independent, random forest classifier is weaker than Semantic Segmentation with Visual transformer, but with a surprisingly small margin. It even manages to outperform the SegNet model.

In this case, the importance of the indices is in Figure 1. The most important is the NDVI which brings another argument to its popularity and usefulness in applications. However, their importance is similar which is remarkable taking into account that all formulas focus on 4 planes. The expert knowledge, incorporated as small tweaks of the weighting coefficients, has visible effects.

Figure 3: Vegetation indices relative importance when various crops have been considered in one-vs-all scenario

One-vs-all. In this case, the problem is a binary classification. The most frequent classes, have been considered as positive labels, while all other as negative. The reason is to see if a vegetation index is more suitable to a specific crop. The most frequent 5 classes (“Bare soil & weed”, “Chinese cabbage”, “Corn”, “Millet”, “Beans”), illustrated in figure 2 have been sequentially considered. Average accuracies for each case are listed in Table 2 . The relative importance of the vegetation indices may be seen in Figure 3. While the order is always different, as each crop is better separated by a specific index, the importance is comparable.

5 Conclusions

Discussion. Vegetation indices have been shown to be powerful discriminatory features, with subtle but relevant differences among them. The popular NDVI is important, but, at least for individual crops, VARI and GNDVI seems to gain the upper hand.

Limitations. The evaluation have been carried in specific conditions: data acquired from UAV, with a specific model of camera. Data used has been internally processed using camera proprietary software for meteorological corrections. The study uses crop from a specific location in China. The vegetation indices list is limited, as presented.

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